

The calibration of FAAM's 2BTechnologies' Ozone photometer model 205 (s/n 1034DB) was performed in FAAM's laboratory on 27/03/2025 using FAAM's 2BTechnologies' Ozone Source model 306 (s/n 238), for the range 0-500 nmol.mol⁻¹.

FAAM's 2BTechnologies' Ozone Source model 306 (s/n 238) was checked against NCAS Primary Standard (Thermo Fisher model TE49i PS, s/n 0703820527) by transferring the NIST reference scale to a Thermo Fisher ozone photometer model TEi49i (Thermo 49i, s/n 730525419) at the NCAS [COZI laboratory](#) in the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry laboratories (WACL) at the University of York on 7/11/2024.

Ozone mole fraction, ppb

Ozone mole fraction from 2BTech model 205 (s/n 1034DB), ppb

Ozone mole fraction from 2BTech model 306 (s/n 238), ppb

Certificate of Ozone Calibrations

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2024-11-25

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Results for #730525419: Model Thermo 49i O3 nmol/mol = 0.99 NCAS COZI O3 nmol/mol – 0.11 nmol/mol

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Results for 1034DB: Model 205 O3 nmol/mol = 1.0093 NCAS COZI O3 nmol/mol – 0.61 nmol/mol

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Uncertainty at amount fractions greater than 100 nmol/mol = ±3% of value. Uncertainty at amount fractions between 0 and 100 nmol/mol = 3nmol/mol.

Reference to NIST Scale

The NCAS Primary Standard (TE49i) #0703820527 is calibrated annually at the National Physical Laboratory against the NIST Standard Reference Photometer SRP 20, quality assured and controlled by independent audit procedures. The calibration performed relates the output from the NCAS TE49i analyser front panel to the ozone amount fractions determined by the SRP.

The most recent NPL calibration (2nd July 2024) of the NCAS Primary Standard reported: -

TE49i nmol/mol = 0.998 SRP20 nmol/mol + 0.5 nmol/mol

FAAM Calibration outline

In this document:-

1. Calibration of core COZI Thermo 49i (O3_4-serial number:-#730525419).
2. Calibration of 2b calibrator using core COZI Thermo 49i (O3_4-serial number:-#730525419).

Calibration was done with lines conditioned prior to calibration with 500ppbV O3, 15 mins at each level with last 10mins used for determining mean and standard deviations.

1. Cal of COZI Thermo O3

2. Cal of FAAM 2b Calibrator

Plot using 1. value from Thermo when dialed up and also plotting both values obtained using O3_4 (thermo and 2b). In summary: O3_4 gives same value using both calibrators and these values are in agreement with dialup.

Summarised data for 2B Calibrator check

Ozone_ppbV_PS	Error_ppbV_PS	Ozone_ppbV_FAAM2B	Error_ppbV_2B
122.28	0.82	122.56	2.49
196.34	0.74	198.18	2.70
148.45	0.59	149.69	3.96
98.58	0.39	98.85	3.85
149.21	0.46	149.65	3.96
-0.15	0.27	0.22	2.70
297.30	1.31	NA	NA
74.93	5.28	73.53	3.09

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Signed:

This work was carried out in the COZI-Lab in the Wolfson Atmospheric Chemistry laboratories (WACL) at the University of York. The COZI-Lab exists to support the UK community and is an Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) from the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS).

THE UNIVERSITY of York

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